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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in our contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
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AN ANALYSIS OF THE LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR THE PROMOTION AND PROTECTION OF HUMAN RIGHTS IN NIGERIA AND SOUTH AFRICA

By

Francis Fwangje,¹ Linda Malchit Daze,² Ogbole Ogancho O.³

Abstract

Human rights violations and abuses are witnessed in Nigeria and South Africa on a daily basis particularly due to insecurity, lack of provision of adequate social amenities, lack of enforcement of socio-economic rights, poverty and corruption. The Human Rights violations and abuses prompted the writing of the paper by examining the legal framework and identifying the lacuna for tackling the challenges. The paper adopted the doctrinal and non-doctrinal methodology in carrying out the research. The objective of the paper was to examine the 1948 United Nations Charter as the global benchmark required by all countries to promote, protect and respect human rights of all its citizens. It has been domesticated as municipal laws in Nigeria and South Africa. The National Human Rights Commission (NHRC) in Nigeria and South Africa was established to complement these efforts on behalf of United Nations at the municipal and regional levels. The paper found out that the National Human Rights Commission in Nigeria performed averagely compared to the South African Human Rights Commission. The paper discovered that the Legal framework in South Africa has provision for the justiciability of socio-economic rights for the citizens. It also discovered that the Legal framework in South Africa has provision for the justiciability of socio-economic rights for the citizens. The article recommended the amendment of the existing institutional and legal framework for the promotion and protection of human rights in Nigeria and South Africa. The article further recommended that it should include a clause with the justiciability of socio-economic rights of citizens.

Keywords: Analysis, Legal framework, Promotion, Protection, Human Rights

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1.0 Introduction

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) was adopted by the United Nations General Assembly on 10th December 1948 to further strengthen international human rights promotion and protection. The UDHR provided common standards for the promotion and protection of human rights for all Peoples and Nations as well as the basis for human rights legal frameworks, municipally, regionally and internationally. It also provided, for the first time in human history, that human rights are classified into civil, political, economic, and cultural rights which all human beings are entitled to at birth. What is clear from this provision is that the fundamental norms of human rights should be respected and protected. But more than that, the UDHR together with the international Covenant on political rights and two optional protocols and the Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights form the Bill of human rights. All these international treaties form the basis for the protection of human rights as ratified by Nigeria and South Africa. Over and above all, governments are expected to put in place domestic measures and legislations compatible with their treaty obligations and duties⁴.

It is pertinent to note that international developments at the General Assembly of the United Nations (UN) in 1993 had an impact on South African's 1993 and Nigeria's 1996 Constitutional provisions pertaining the establishment and the role of some of its constitutional bodies particularly the National Human Rights Commissions of Nigeria and the South Africa Human Rights Commission. The Vienna Declaration and the programme of action adopted at the World Conference on Human rights in 1993 recognised the importance of National institutions for the promotion and protection of human rights especially their role in addressing human rights violations and in the dissemination of information and education on human rights.⁵ The Paris Principles covers four principal areas namely: the responsibilities and competence of national institutions, composition of National Human Rights Institutions (NHRIs) including the guarantee of independence and pluralism, *modus operandi* of NHRIs and quasi-judicial functions, that is, the power to hear and adjudicate on complaints or petitions

⁴ Article 55 of the United Nations Charter.

⁵ Vienna Declaration and Programme of Action, Note 1, 1, 36.

on individual situations. In addition to the Paris Principles, political will and an effective judiciary are other factors that are necessary for the success of NHRIs.⁶

The word 'right' means that a person has a just and valid claim, be it on a land, a thing or the privilege of doing something. 'Human' pertains⁷ to having characteristics of, or the nature of mankind. Human rights are thus rights which all persons everywhere, and at all times have by virtue of being mortal and rational creatures. The Constitution is the grundnorm of the country's corpus juris. Therefore, Human Rights are enshrined in the Constitution and are enforceable in accordance with the provisions of the Constitution. In *Kuti and others v. AG Federation*⁸, Oputa JSC emphasized that not every civil or legal right is fundamental rights. The ideal and concept of fundamental rights both derive from the premise of the inalienable rights of man - life, liberty, and the pursuit of happiness. Emergent Nations with written constitutions have enshrined in such constitutions some of these basic human rights, thus spelling each right that is considered fundamental.

In Nigeria, those constitutional rights that are considered fundamental to human beings are enshrined in Chapter IV of the Constitution of Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended),⁹ particularly Sections 33 to 46, and the African Charter on Human and Peoples Rights. These are rights that are enforceable in our Courts of law in Nigeria and South Africa. These rights that are contained in Chapter IV of the Nigerian Constitution are referred to as first generation rights¹⁰ – right to life - section 33, right to dignity of human person - section 34, right to personal liberty - Section 35, right to fair hearing – section 36, right to private and family life - Section 37, right to freedom of thought, conscience and religion - Section 38, right to freedom of expression and press – Section 39, right to peaceful assembly and association Section 40, right to freedom of movement, section 41, right to freedom from discrimination - Section 42, right to acquire and own immovable property anywhere in Nigeria – Section 43,

⁶ United Nations (UN) Economic, Social and Cultural Rights: A Handbook for National Human Rights Geneva, 2005). P.32.

⁷ ManjotKaur. *Teaching Human Rights*. APH Publishing Corporation, New Delhi 2008, p. 1.

⁸ [1985] 8 NWLR (Pt 6) 211.

⁹ Ss.33 to 36 Constitution of Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended).

¹⁰ First generation rights largely represent Western liberal democratic ideas which, in the views of Adamantia Pollis, are anchored on a definition of a person as (an isolated, autonomous individual). It is a categorization of rights as they evolved and in accordance with their importance. See also Eze, O.C. *Human Right Law*, No. 1 (Lagos: Helen-Roberts Limited, 1997) at 2-3.

compulsory acquisition of property – Section 44, restriction on the derogation from Fundamental Rights.

The enforcement of these rights are not without challenges and the challenges that arise in the enforcement of these rights under the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended) and Constitution of the Republic of South Africa motivated this study. The objective of the paper is to analyse the legal framework for the promotion and protection of human rights in Nigeria and South Africa and comparative lessons of the research. Unfortunately, despite the robust legislation and legal framework for the promotion and protection of Human rights in Nigeria and South Africa, there are incessant cases of human rights abuses and violations which prompted this research. The research adopted the doctrinal and non-doctrinal research methodology in carrying out the study.

It is important to state from the outset that fundamental Human Rights provisions have continued to feature very prominently in successive constitutions of the Federal Republic of Nigeria and South Africa. The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1979 provided for the Constitutional recognition of human rights through the Fundamental Objectives and Directive Principles of State Policy (Chapter II)¹¹ while that of the Republic of South Africa's Constitution of 1996 contains the provisions of the bill of rights. The National Human Rights Commission of Nigeria was established by National Human Rights Commission Act 1995 in line with the resolution of the United Nations which enjoins all member states to establish human rights institutions for the promotion and protection of human rights¹². The South Africa Human Rights Commission was established as an independent institution supporting constitutional democracy, established in terms of Chapter 9 of the Constitution which made specific mandate for the Commission as stipulated in section 184 of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa 1996. The Commission is saddled with the responsibility to promote, respect for human rights and a culture of human rights, promote the protection, development and attainment of human rights and monitor and assess the observation of human rights in South Africa.¹³

¹¹ Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1979.

¹² Section 5(a) National Human Rights Commission Act CAP N45LFN, 2014 (herein after referred to as NHRC Act).

¹³ South African Human Rights Act. Act 54 of 1994 Powers and Functions of South African Human Rights Commission.

In Nigeria, the inability of the Government to promote and protect the rights of its citizens is a negation of constitutional responsibility as enshrined in section 14 (b)-(c) of Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended) thus, the security and welfare of the people shall be the primary purpose of the Government and the participation by the people in their Government shall be ensured in accordance with the provisions of the constitution.¹⁴

The negation of Constitutional responsibility has paved way for insecurity and terrorist attacks as quoted below:

The global Terrorism index in 2017 ranked Nigeria as the fourth country¹⁵ with the highest number of deaths resulting from terrorism after Iraq, Afghanistan and Syria as about 1,832 deaths were caused by terror attacks in 2016. Similarly, the International Crisis Group, and International NGO war on prevention has reported that the Fulani herdsmen violence has claimed six times more lives than Boko Haram insurgency in 2018... has revealed that armed banditry has claimed more than 6,319 lives, widowed 4,983 with 25,050 children and 190,340 persons displaced.

The identified challenges motivated the need to examine the legal framework for the promotion and protection of human rights in Nigeria and South Africa despite the legal framework in place for promoting and protecting human rights.

The paper examined the institutional and international Human Right treaties, conventions and municipal laws for the promotion and protection of human rights in Nigeria and South Africa as follows:

2.0 International Legal Framework of Human Rights

2.1 The Universal Declaration on Human Rights¹⁶

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) affirms the universal recognition of the inherent dignity, equal and inalienable rights of all members of human family as the foundation of freedom, justice and peace in the world.¹⁷ Human rights have been

¹⁴ Akande Jadesola, *Introduction to the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria*, (Malthouse Publishers 1999), p.54.

¹⁵ The light Bearer Newspaper, "Need for a Decisive Action Against Insecurity" October, 2019 p.4.

¹⁶ See generally *Bowett's Law of International Institutions* (eds. P. Sands and P. Klein), 6th edn, Manchester, 2 Lauterpacht, *International Law*, pp. 145-220; *UN Action in the Field of Human Rights*, New York, 1981, and *Hu*

Rights: Thirty Years after the Universal Declaration (ed. B. Ramcharan), Dordrecht, 1979.

¹⁷ Preamble of the Universal Declaration of Human Right, para 1.

identified as encompassing and embracing the rights all humans are entitled to. These rights amongst others included civil and political rights such as right to life and liberty, dignity, equality before the law and freedom of expression,¹⁸ also included are right to work, education, participation in culture and economic rights. Therefore, all forms of discrimination either by reason of race, color, sex, creed, religion or whatever sentiment are contrary to the Human Rights standard in UDHR.¹⁹ The declaration condemns in unmistakable terms any principle that makes it impossible for those rights to freedom from discriminations to flourish. Also, in recognition of these rights, there are always attempts in different countries to limit their enforcement, either through constitutional provisions, legislative enactments, or decrees especially by undemocratic regimes.²⁰

The United Nations is mandated to promote universal respect for and observance of human rights.²¹ In the same vein, article 56 states that all members pledge themselves to take joint and separate action in cooperation with the organisation for the achievement of the purposes set forth in article 55.²² It was as a result of the international law provisions that countries were mandatorily required to promote and protect human rights inclusive of Nigeria and South Africa. The hardship experienced during the Second World War resulted in the world leaders to consider the need to establish a global organization for the effective promotion and protection of human rights as one of the essential conditions of international peace and progress.

The provision in Article 68 of the UN Charter which mandates the Economic and Social Council shall set up a commission in economic and social field and for the protection of human rights. In January, 1946 the Commission on Human Rights was constituted by the UN Economic and Social Council with the principal task of preparing the texts of an International Bill of Rights, international declarations and convention on human rights. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights was adopted and proclaimed by the UN General Assembly on 10 December, 1948:

¹⁸ Article 1, Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

¹⁹ Article 2, Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

²⁰ Decree justifying Administrative Detention of Military opponent, known as Security (Detention) of Persons Decree No. 2 of 1984 during General Buhari Regime, See Section 33 (1) (2) (a-c) 1999 Constitution of Federal Republic of Nigeria.

²¹ Article 55 of the UN Charter.

²² Under article 62, the Economic and Social Council has the power to make recommendations for the purpose promoting respect for and observance of human rights.

as a common standard of achievement for all peoples and all nations, to the end that every individual and every organ of society, keeping this Declaration constantly in mind, shall strive by teaching and education to promote respect for these rights and freedoms and by progressive measures, national and international, to secure their universal and effective recognition and observance, both among the peoples of Member States themselves and among the peoples of territories under their jurisdiction.²³

The preamble of the UN Charter proclaims, 'a common standard of achievement for all peoples and nations'. There are thirty articles which include many rights ranging from liberty and security of the person²⁴, equality before the law, effective remedies, due process, prohibitions on torture and arbitrary interference with privacy to rights protecting freedom of movement, asylum, expression, conscience and religion and assembly. It is worthy to note that the Declaration included social and economic rights such as the right to work and equal pay, the right to social security and the right to education.²⁵ The Declaration had a marked influence upon the constitutions of many states and upon the formulation of subsequent human rights treaties and resolutions.²⁶ In 1968, the Proclamation of Tehran at the conclusion of the UN-sponsored International Conference on Human Rights stressed that the Declaration constituted 'an obligation for members of the international community'.²⁷ The

²³ See e.g. *Oppenheim's International Law* (eds. R. Y. Jennings and A. D. Watts, 9th edn, London, 1992), p. 1001; M. Whiteman, *Digest of International Law*, Washington, 1965, vol. V, p. 237; J. Humphrey, 'The Universal Declaration on Human Rights' in Ramcharan, *Human Rights*, p. 21; J. Kunz, 'The United Nations Declaration of Human Rights', 43 *AJIL*, 1949, p. 316; E. Schwelb, 'The Influence of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights on International and National Law', *PASIL*, 1959, p. 217; A. Verdoodt, *Naissance et Signification de la Declaration Universelle de Droits de l'Homme*, Paris, 1964; *The Universal Declaration of Human Rights: A Commentary* (eds. A. Eide, G. Alfredsson, G. Melander, L. A. Rehof and A. Rosas), Dordrecht, 1992; *The Universal Declaration of Human Rights: A Common Standard of Achievement* (eds. G. Alfredsson and A. Eide), The Hague, 1999, and P. R. Ghandi, 'The Universal Declaration of Human Rights at 50 Years', 41 *German YIL*, 1998, p. 206.

²⁴ Article 3 UN Charter.

²⁵ See Articles 3 – 26 of UN Charter.

²⁶ See e.g. Schwelb, 'Influence'; J. Humphrey, 'The International Bill of Rights: Scope and Implementation', 17 *William and Mary Law Review*, 1975, p. 527; *Oppenheim's International Law*, pp. 1002-5; Judge Tanaka, *South-West Africa cases*, ICJ Reports, 1966, pp. 6, 288 -*am* 233-, 37 pp. 243, 454, and the European Convention on Human Rights, 1950, below, chapter 7, p. 250.

²⁷ 23 GAOR, A/Conf. 32/41. See also the non-governmental Montreal Statement, 9 *Review of the International Commission of Jurists*, 1968, p. 94.

Declaration has also been referred to in many cases,²⁸ and its importance within the context of United Nations human rights law should not be disregarded.²⁹ A number of important international conventions dealing with selective human rights issues including the Genocide Convention³⁰ and the Convention on the Elimination of Racial Discrimination were adopted.³¹

The Declaration is a binding legal instrument. Some of its provisions either constitute the general principles of law or represent elementary considerations of humanity.³² The Universal Declaration made up of the International Bill of Human Rights, were: the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, the International Covenants on Civil and Political Rights and the Optional Protocol. It provided international machinery for dealing with communication with individuals claiming to be victims of abuses and violations of any of the rights set forth in that Covenant which entered into force in 1976. The Covenant on Civil and Political Rights provides³³ for the Human Rights Committee with the responsibility of considering reports from states and addressing issues relating to human rights promotion and protection and to the U.N Economic and Social Council. The Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural rights contain various articles in which member countries are required to promote and protect, such rights as the right to work, to social security, the right of everyone to an adequate standard of living for himself and his family, the rights to health, education etcetera.

The Vienna Declaration adopted by the World Conference on Human Rights (1993) states:

²⁸ See e.g. *In re Flesche* 16 AD, pp. 266, 269; *The State (Duggan J v. Tapley* 18 ILR, pp. 336, 342; *Robinson v. Secretary- General of the UN* 19 ILR, pp. 494,496; *Extradition of Greek National* case, 22 ILR, pp. 520, 524 and *Beth El Mission v. Minister of Social Welfare* 47 ILR, pp. 205, 207. See also *Corfu Channel* case, ICJ Reports, 1949, pp. 4, 22; 16 AD, pp. 155, 158 and *Filartiga v. Pena-Irala* 630 F.2d 876 (1980).

²⁹ The Vienna Declaration and Programme of Action adopted on 25 June 1993 at the UN Conference on Human Rights referred to the Declaration as the 'source of inspiration' and the 'basis for the United Nations in making advances in standard setting as contained in the existing international human rights instruments', 32 ILM, 1993, pp. 1661, 1663. The private International Law Association adopted a resolution in 1994 in which it noted that 'the Universal Declaration of Human Rights is universally regarded as an authoritative elaboration of the human rights provisions of the United Nations Charter' and that 'many if not all of the rights elaborated in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights are widely recognised as constituting rules of customary international law', Report of the Sixty-sixth Conference, Buenos Aires, 1994, p. 29.

³⁰ See below, p. 205.

³¹ See further below, p. 208.

³² Nevertheless, the 1968 Teheran UN Conference on Human Rights was able to declare that the Declaration constituted "an obligation" for the members of the international community.

³³ Article 41.

All human rights are universal, indivisible, and interdependent and interrelated. The international community must treat human rights globally in a fair and equal manner, on the same footing, and with the same emphasis. While the significance of national and religious background must be borne in mind, it is the duty of states, regardless of their political, economic and cultural systems, to promote and protect all human rights and fundamental freedom.³⁴

The UN Centre for Human Rights initiated the establishment of a UN High Commissioner for Human Rights. The post of UN High Commissioner for Human Rights was indeed established several months later³⁵ and filled in April 1994. The General Assembly resolution 48/141 provided that the UN High Commissioner for Human Rights would be the UN Official with principal responsibility for UN human rights activities³⁶ and the protection of the collective rights of groups and individuals³⁷.

2.2 The International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR)

The International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights was adopted in 1966 and entered into force in 1976. The Article 2 of the Covenant provides that each state party undertakes to take steps to maximise its available resources to achieving progressively the full realisation of the rights recognised in the Covenant'. The rights included self-determination³⁸, the right to work³⁹, the right to social security⁴⁰,

³⁴ See also paragraph 13 of the Proclamation of the Conference on Human Rights, Tehran (1948) which states, inter-alia, "Since human rights and fundamental freedoms are indivisible, the full realization of civil and political liberties without the enjoyment of economic, social and cultural rights is almost impossible."

³⁵ See General Assembly resolution 48/141, 20 December 1993. See also A. Clapham, 'Creating the High Commissioner for Human Rights: The Outside Story', 5 EJIL, 1994.

³⁶ The High Commissioner is responsible for promoting and protecting the effective enjoyment by all of all civil, cultural, economic, political and social rights, providing through the UN Centre for Human Rights and other appropriate institutions, advisory services and other assistance including education and engaging in dialogue with all governments with a view to securing respect for human rights. The High Commissioner may also make recommendations to competent bodies of the UN system with a view to improving the promotion and protection of all human rights, see the first Report of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights, 1995, A/49/36.

³⁷ Sanders, D. 'Collective Rights', 13 HRQ, 1991, p. 368, and N. Lerner, *Group Rights and Discrimination in International Law*, 2nd edn, The Hague, 2003.

³⁸ Article 1 of the ICESCR.

³⁹ Article 6 and 7 of the ICESCR.

⁴⁰ Article 9 of the ICESCR.

adequate standard of living⁴¹ and education⁴² to the right to take part in cultural life and enjoy the benefits of scientific progress and its applications⁴³. The Covenant stated that parties were obliged to send periodic reports to ECOSOC.⁴⁴ In 1978, a Sessional Working Group was constituted consisting of fifteen members elected by ECOSOC from amongst states parties for three-year renewable terms. The Group met annually and reported to the Council. In 1987, the new Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights commenced operation.⁴⁵ Unlike the Racial Discrimination Committee, the Human Rights Committee and the Torture Committee, the Economic Committee is not autonomous; rather, it is accountable to a principal organ of the United Nations, namely ECOSOC, and not to the States Parties. Nigeria ratified the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) on July 29 1993 while South Africa ratified the ICESCR on January 12th 2015.

2.3 International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) 1966⁴⁶

The Covenant incorporated almost all the civil and political rights in the UDHR. Women enjoy plethora of rights under this instrument though it excluded such rights as the right to property. Some of its provisions relevant to the rights of women are as follows: the ICCPR enjoins state parties to the covenant to protect the civil and political rights of their citizens as contained in the covenant. It prohibits sex discrimination with provision to the effect that each state party shall undertake to respect and ensure to all individuals within its territory and subject to its jurisdiction the rights recognized in the convention, without distinction of any kind, such as color, sex, race, language,

⁴¹Article 11 of the ICESCR.

⁴²Article 13 of the ICESCR.

⁴³Article 15 of the ICESCR.

⁴⁴ See articles 16-22 of the Covenant, and *UN Chronicle*, July 1982. See generally on implementation B. S. Ramcharan, 'Implementing the International Covenants on Human Rights' in Ramcharan, *Human Rights: Thirty Years After the Universal Declaration*; P. Alston, 'Out of the Abyss: The Challenge Confronting the New UN Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights', 9 HRQ, 1987; P. Alston and G. Quinn, 'The Nature and Scope of States Parties' Obligations under the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights', 9 HRQ, 1987; P. Alston, 'The Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights' in Alston, *United Nations and Human Rights*; B. Simma, 'The Implementation of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights' in *The Implementation of Economic, Social and Cultural Rights* (ed. F. Matscher), Kehl am Rhein, 1991 and S. Leckie, 'The Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights' in Alston and Crawford, *Future*, chapter 6.

⁴⁵ See P. Alston and B. Simma, 'First Session of the UN Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights', 81 AJIL, 1987 and 'Second Session of the UN Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights', 82 AJIL, 1988. See generally www.ohchr.org/en/hrbodies/cescr/pages/cescrindex.aspx.

⁴⁶ The International Covenant on Civil and Political rights was adopted by the General Assembly on the 16 December, 1966 and came into force on 23 March 1976.

religion, political opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status.⁴⁷ The covenant accordingly enjoins state parties, to undertake to ensure the equal rights of men and women to the enjoyment of all civil and political rights set out in the covenant. The civil and political rights of citizens which the parties are enjoined to protect as contained in the covenant.⁴⁸ In addition, a remarkable provision of ICCPR is the right to self-determination by virtue of which all peoples have the right to freely determine their political status and their economic, social and cultural development.⁴⁹ This unique provision serves as a check on the powers of the state party, to hide under the principle of sovereignty to ill-treat or oppress any group of people within its territory, since every group has a right under the ICCPR to agitate for political autonomy.⁵⁰ This provision is a significant departure from the Universal Declaration which was conceived as a charter for individual rights.⁵¹ Though these rights, as entrenched in the ICCPR are not absolute, they could be derogated upon by state parties during a public emergency which threatens the security of the nation. But the derogation must not be inconsistent with the state party's obligation under International Law and should not involve discrimination solely on race, sex, color, language, religion and social origin. Again, the derogation must be reasonable and in accordance with existing law in force.⁵² Nigeria ratified the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights on July 29 1993 while South Africa ratified the ICCPR on December 10, 1998, with the covenant entering into force in March 1999.

2.4 The Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination Against Women

The Commission on the Status of Women was established in 1946 as one of the functional Commissions of ECOSOC and plays a role both in standard-setting and in the elaboration of further relevant instruments.⁵³ The Committee on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women was established under article 22 of the

⁴⁷ Article 2(1) of the ICESCR.

⁴⁸ Articles 6-13 of the ICESCR.

⁴⁹ Ogbu, op.cit p. 45.

⁵⁰ Ibid, p.45.

⁵¹ Ibid, p.45.

⁵² Ibid, p.45.

⁵³ See ECOSOC resolutions 1/5 (1946), 2/11 (1946) and 48 (IV) (1947). See also L. Reanda, 'The Commission on the Status of Women' in Alston, *United Nations and Human Rights*, p. 265. The mandate of the Commission was revised by ECOSOC resolutions 1987/22 and 1996/6. There is also an individual petition procedure by which complaints are considered by a Working Group on Communications which then reports to the Commission. The Commission in turn reports to ECOSOC.

1979 Convention on the Elimination of all Forms of Discrimination Against Women.⁵⁴ The Convention is implemented by means of states' reports and it was composed of twenty-three experts serving in individual capacities for four-year terms. It held its first regular session in October 1982 and at its second session examined the reports of seven state parties regarding measures taken to comply with the terms of the Convention. It reports annually to the UN General Assembly through ECOSOC.⁵⁵ The Committee has provided guidelines to state parties on reporting, whereby initial reports were intended to be detailed and comprehensive with subsequent reports being of an updating nature.⁵⁶ Since 1990, subsequent reports were examined first by a pre-sessional working group. Following discussion of a report, the Committee provided concluding comments. The Committee, in addition to hearing states' reports, may make suggestions and general recommendations, which were included in the report.⁵⁷ Since 1997, the process of adopting a general recommendation was preceded by an open dialogue between the Committee, non-governmental organisations and others regarding the human rights issues.

The Optional Protocol adopted in 1999 and in force as from December 2000 allows for the right of individual petition provided that a number of conditions are met, including the requirement for the exhaustion of domestic remedies. Also, the Protocol created an inquiry procedure enabling the Committee to initiate inquiries into situations of grave or systematic violations of women's rights where it has received reliable information of grave or systematic violations by a state party of rights established in the Convention.⁵⁸ The importance of women's rights has received

⁵⁴ This came into force in 1981. See Rehman, *International Human Rights Law*, chapter 15; R. Jacobson, 'The Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women' in Alston, *United Nations and Human Rights*, p. 444; A. Byrnes, 'The "Other" Human Rights Body: The Work of the Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination Against Women', 14 *Yale Journal of International Law*, 1989, p. 1; R. Cook, 'Women's International Human Rights Law', 15 HRQ, 1993, p. 230; *Human Rights of Women* (ed. R. Cook), Philadelphia, 1994; M. Freeman and A. Fraser, 'Women's Human Rights' in Herlin and Hargrove, *Human Rights: An Agenda for the Next Century*, p. 103; Steiner, Alston and Goodman, *International Human Rights*, pp. 175 and 541; J. Morsink, 'Women's Rights in the Universal Declaration', 13 HRQ, 1991, p. 229; H. Charlesworth and C. Chinkin, *The Boundaries of International Law: A Feminist Analysis*, Manchester, 2000, and M. Bustelo, 'The Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women at the Crossroads' in Alston and Crawford, *Future*, p. 79.

⁵⁵ See articles 17-21 of the Convention and the first Report of the Committee, A/38/45, and *UN Chronicle*, November 1983.

⁵⁶ See CEDAW/C/7Rev.3 and with regard to reports submitted from 1 January 2003, www.un.org/womenwatch/daw/cedaw/guidelines.PDF.

⁵⁷ Article 21, CEDAW.

⁵⁸ Article 8 of the Optional Protocol. See, for example, for an earlier view, R. Cook, 'The Elimination of Sexual Apartheid: Prospects for the Fourth World Conference on Women', *ASIL Issue Papers on World Conferences*, Washington, 1995.

greater recognition. The Vienna Declaration and Programme of Action adopted in 1993 emphasised that the human rights of women should be brought into the mainstream of United Nations system-wide activity and that women's rights should be regularly and systematically addressed throughout the UN bodies and mechanisms.⁵⁹ In furtherance to the provision, the fifth meeting of Chairpersons of Human Rights Treaty Bodies in 1994 agreed that the enjoyment of the human rights of women by each treaty body within the competence of its mandate should be closely monitored. The Special Rapporteur on Torture was called upon by the Commission on Human Rights in 1994 to examine questions concerning torture directed disproportionately or primarily against women.⁶⁰

In addition, the General Assembly adopted a Declaration on the Elimination of Violence Against Women in February 1994,⁶¹ and a Special Rapporteur on Violence against Women, its Causes and Consequences was appointed in 1994.⁶² The International Labour Organization established the promotion of equality of opportunity and treatment of men and women in employment as a priority item in its programme and budget for 1994/95.⁶³ The Committee on the Rights of the Child considers the issue of the 'Girl-Child' and the question of Child prostitution.⁶⁴ There were rampant cases of human rights abuses and violations in Nigeria and South Africa particularly Child marriage, Labour, Molestation, Prostitution, etcetera. South Africa ratified the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination and the Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhumane or Degrading Treatment or Punishment on the 10th December 1998. Considering South Africa's history of apartheid, where civil and political rights, such as the right of non-discrimination,

⁵⁹ See Part II, Section 3, 32 ILM, 1993. See also the Beijing Conference 1995, Cook, 'Elimination of Sexual Apartheid'; the Beijing plus 5 process, see General Assembly resolution 55/71. In 2000, the General Assembly adopted resolution S-23/3 containing a Political Declaration and a statement on further actions and initiatives to implement the Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action.

⁶⁰ See resolution 1994/37. See also the Report of the Special Rapporteur of January 1995, E/CN.4/1995/34.

⁶¹ Resolution 48/104, see 33 ILM, 1994. Note also the adoption of the Inter-American Convention on the Prevention, Punishment and Eradication of Violence Against Women in June 1994, *ibid.* and the March 2002 Joint Declaration by the Special Rapporteur on women's rights of the Inter-American Commission on Human Rights, the Special Rapporteur on Violence Against Women, its Causes and its Consequences of the UN Commission on Human Rights, and the Special Rapporteur on the Rights of Women in Africa of the African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights which called for the elimination of violence and discrimination against women: see www.cidh.org/declaration.women.htm.

⁶² See E/CN.4/2003/75.

⁶³ E/CN.4/Sub.2/1994/5, p. 6.

⁶⁴ See further below, p. 238.

freedom of movement and freedom of association, were routinely denied, the full implementation of the rights contained within the ICCPR are critical to the realisation of an equal and just society imagined in South Africa's Constitution of 1996.⁶⁵ Nigeria ratified the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women in 1985.

2.5 African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights

The adoption of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights in 1948 was followed by regional efforts towards the promotion and protection of human rights. In responding to the declaration, the 18th Assembly of Heads of States and Governments of the Organisation of African Unity (OAU) meeting in Nairobi, Kenya adopted the African Charter in 1981. The regional African human rights system was predicated on the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights, which came into force on the 21st October 1986. Nigeria and South Africa are member countries of OAU (now AU), and had ratified the Charter as a municipal law. The African Charter on Human and Peoples Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act (Cap A9 2011) Law of the Federation of Nigeria 2004 by Section 1 of the Act stated that as from the commencement of the Act, the provisions of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights which are set out in the schedule to the act shall, subject as hereunder provided, have force of law in Nigeria and shall be given full recognition and effect and be applied by all authorities and persons exercising legislative, executive or judicial powers in Nigeria.⁶⁶ The judiciary in Nigeria has interpreted the above to mean that the African charter is now enforceable by municipal courts in the country. In *Ogugu v. State*⁶⁷, the Supreme Court held that:

Since the African Charter on Human and Peoples rights has become part of our domestic laws, the enforcement of its provisions like our other laws fall within the judicial powers of the court as provided by the constitution and all other laws relating thereto... the human and peoples' rights of the African Charter are enforceable by the several high courts depending on the circumstances of each case and in accordance with the rules, practice and procedure of each court⁶⁸.

⁶⁵ Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, Act 108 of 1996.

⁶⁶ Section 1 of the Ratification and Enforcement Act (Cap 10) Law of the Federation of Nigeria 1990.

⁶⁷ (1994)9 NWLR (Part 366) 1

⁶⁸ Ezeilo J. op.cit, p.48.

In *Fawehinmi v. General Sani Abacha*⁶⁹, the Court of Appeal restated the domestic application of the Charter and held that the Charter has superior application to municipal laws including the constitution and decrees of the military government. In June 1998, the OAU adopted and approved the Protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples' rights upon the establishment of an African Court on Human and Peoples' Rights.⁷⁰ The African Human Rights Court is envisioned to support the promotion and protection of Human rights in Africa⁷¹ to the African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights which is the body that has carried out series of continental and central oversight over human rights functions since 1987.⁷² The Protocol affirms that the African Human Rights Court would be a factor for advancement and the protection of human rights within the regional system for efficient and effective enforcement of a human rights regime. Nigeria ratified the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights in 1983 while South Africa acceded to it in 1996. Nigeria's ratification was through the African Charter on Human and People's Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act, which made it enforceable in Nigerian courts. South Africa's accession occurred later, after the end of the apartheid.

3.0 Municipal Legal Framework in Nigeria

3.1 Constitution of Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended)

The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended) provided the legal framework for democratic governance and entrenchment of fundamental Human rights of its citizens in Nigeria effective from 29th May, 1999. The Constitution is the grundnorm which enshrined the bill of rights enumerated as follows:⁷³ right to life, right to dignity of human persons, right to personal liberty, right to fair hearing, right to compensation for property compulsorily acquired, right to private and family life, right to freedom of thought, conscience and religion, right to freedom of expression, right to freedom of movement and right to freedom from discrimination on the

⁶⁹ (1996) 9 NWLR (Pt 475) 710.

⁷⁰ Protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights on the Establishment of an African Court on Human and Peoples' Rights, Assembly of Heads of State and Government of the Organization of African Unity, Ouagadougou, Burkina Faso, June 1998, OAU/LEG/MIN/AFCHPR/PROT (1). (Hereinafter Protocol).

⁷¹ The Protocol shall enter into force thirty days after ratification by fifteen OAU member States, Protocol, supra note 3, Article 34. Although by April 1999, the Protocol had been signed by 30 states, only two, Burkina Faso and Senegal, had ratified it.

⁷² OAU Convention Governing the Specific Aspects of Refugee Problems in Africa, done September 10, 1969, reprinted in 8 ILM 1288 (1969).

⁷³ Sections 34, 35, 36, 37, 38 CFRN, 1999 (as amended).

grounds of ethnic groups, place of origin, circumstances of birth, sex, religion or political opinion.

The combined efforts of Sections 42, 16(1) (b), 17 and 19(c) of the Constitution is the protection of citizen's rights to non-discrimination and equality before and equal protection of the law. The provision in Section 45 of the Constitution relates to the restriction of fundamental rights enshrined in the Constitution. The rights provided for in Sections 37 to 41 are granted to every person within the territory of Nigeria and may be restricted or derogated from by any law that is reasonably justifiable in a democratic society, in the interest of defence, public safety, public order, public morality or public health. Section 45(2)⁷⁴ provides that the rights to life and personal liberty can be derogated from, in the event of war or during a period of emergency as provided for under section 305 of the Constitution. Under the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended), social, economic and cultural rights are provided for under the Chapter II. However, these rights are not guaranteed to the citizens of Nigeria. It should be noted that Section 13 of the Constitution states: "it shall be the duty and responsibility of all organs of government, and of all authorities and persons, exercising legislative, executive or judicial powers, to conform to..."

In *Archbishop Anthony Olubunmi Okogie (Trustee of Roman-Catholic School) v. Attorney-General of Lagos State*,⁷⁵ the Court held that the Directive Principles of State Policy in Chapter II have to be in harmony and are to run ancillary to the fundamental rights, and that Chapter II is subject to legislative powers. It is important to note that the only economic right guaranteed under fundamental rights provision of the Constitution is found in Section 43⁷⁶ which grants the right to acquire and own immovable property. This reflects the English constitutional tradition which assumes that socio-economic rights by their nature do not lead themselves to judicial enforcement as mere manifestoes. The intention is for those who run the affairs of the state to have some basic guidelines about core values of constitutional democracy. All authorities, legislative, executives and judicial powers are under the duty and responsibility to conform to, observe and apply the fundamental objectives and directive principles of state policy. However, under section 6 (6) (c) of the Constitution

⁷⁴ Section 45 (2) CFRN, 1999 (as amended).

⁷⁵ (1981) 1 NCLR 218.

⁷⁶ Section 43 of CFRN, 1999 (as amended).

of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended), the fundamental objectives and directive principles are non-justiciable.

In South Africa, social, cultural and economic rights are justiciable and thus enforceable in the Courts of law. But the question remains whether civil and political rights such as the right to life, dignity and liberty can be separated from the social rights. The argument here is that these rights cannot be appreciated with the non-existence of social and welfare facilities. Nwabueze,⁷⁷ has written that the Constitution's refusal to recognize its citizens of their social and economic rights to tally with their civil and political rights... lays claim to no more than mere political existence. Its provisions are essentially political not legal serving as mere exhortations to direct and inspire government action and to bestow upon them the stamp of legitimacy".⁷⁸ This reasoning has been echoed by the Supreme Court in India, in *Francis Coralie v. Union Territory of India*,⁷⁹ where it held that:

The right to life includes the right to live with human dignity and all that goes with it, namely the bare necessities of life such as adequate nutrition, clothing and shelter... the magnitude and components of this right would depend upon the extent of economic development of the country, but it must, in any view of the matter, include the bare necessities of life.

3.2 Judiciary

The judiciary is responsible for adjudication on the rights of citizens and final arbiter in the country. According to *Black's Law Dictionary*,⁸⁰ judiciary is that branch of government invested with the judicial power; the system of courts in a country; the body of judges; the bench; that branch of government which is intended to interpret, construe and apply the law.

The judiciary plays a vital role in checkmating the excesses of the executive and legislature and ensuring constitutionalism and the rule of law are applicable in all facets of life in the country.

⁷⁷ Ben Nwabueze, 'Fundamental Objectives and Directive Principles of State Policy: Its nature' Daily Times (Lagos, 1977) 49.

⁷⁸ J. N. Aduba, "The Constitutionality of the Justiciability Question" in *Justiciability and Constitutionalism* (Nigerian Institute of Advanced Legal Studies, 2010) 116.

⁷⁹ AIR 1978 SC 597.9.

⁸⁰ "West edition, p. 762. 33.

Nnamani describes the role of judiciary as follows:⁸¹

It has been generally acknowledged that the judiciary is the guardian of our Constitution, the protector of our cherished governance under the Rule of Law, the guardian of our fundamental rights, the enforcer of all the laws without which the stability of society can be threatened, the maintainer of public order and public security, the guarantee against arbitrariness and generally the only insurance for a just and happy society.

The above definitions are pointers to the role of the judiciary as the custodian of judicial power. The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended) in Section 6(1) and (2) provides:

- 1) The judicial powers of the Federation shall be vested in the courts to which this section relates being courts established for the Federation.
- 2) The judicial powers of a state shall be vested in the courts to which this section relates, being courts established subject as provided by this Constitution, for a State.⁸²

According to Miller,⁸³ the judicial power is the power of the Court to decide and pronounce a judgment and carry it out into effect between parties and persons who brought the case before the Court.

3.3 Legislature

The Senate and House of Representatives have committees on human rights, judiciary and legal matters responsible for an oversight function of National Human Rights Institutions and supervisory ministries in order to ensure effective promotion and protection of human rights consistent with Nigeria's International obligations. The National Assembly had enacted and ratified some international protocols, conventions and charters as follows:

- i. National Action Plan on Human Rights Project, ratification of international human rights instruments
- ii. Human rights legislations; Child Rights Act 2003.

⁸¹ The Judiciary in the 1990s: Expectation and Challenges," in *Justice; A Journal of Contemporary Legal Problems*, Vol. I, No.3 (1990).

⁸² Section 6(1) and (2) of the CFRN, 1999 (as amended).

⁸³ On the Constitution (New York: 1991).

- iii. The Committee on Human Rights, National Working Group on prison decongestion; parliamentary working group on justice sector reform; commonwealth human rights forum
- iv. Promotional activities of the Committee on human rights: visit to the National Refugees Commission; visit to the national human rights commission; convene meetings with government and non-governmental organizations saddled with the responsibility of promoting human rights municipally, regional and globally, participation at the United Nations Human Rights Commission's Session

Nigeria's ratification on international human rights instruments include National/State Houses of Assembly consultative forum on adopting appropriate legislation for the promotion and protection of the rights of Children; parliamentary working group on justice sector reform; protecting the right of women; the death penalty debate: public participation in the House of Representatives, monitoring economic and social rights; quarterly publication on the activities of the work of the committee/parliamentary report on the state of human rights in Nigeria.

3.3.1 Legislative Enactments and Policy Frameworks

The Constitution guarantees fundamental human rights and impose obligations on the state and non-state actors to ensure their effective realization. The legislative arm enacted some laws for the promotion and protection of human rights in Nigeria especially the rights of vulnerable groups such as Women, Children, Refugees and Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs), victims of trafficking and forced labour, persons living with HIV/AIDS, etcetera. The enacted laws are as follows:

(1) Child Rights Act 2003

The Child Rights Act 2003 domesticates the survival, development, protection and participatory rights of Children as guaranteed under the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child and African Union Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child. The Child Rights Act in Section 21 seeks to protect women/girls against early marriage by stipulating 18 years as age of marriage. The Child Rights Act provides the legal framework for State legislations dealing with individual aspects of Child protection, particularly the prohibition of Child hawking, Child begging, Child trafficking, all forms of labour, sexual and economic exploitation of Children, harmful traditional practices affecting Children such as Child marriage and betrothal, withdrawal of children from schools for hawking or begging or marriage, Female Genital Mutilation (FGM) etcetera. Furthermore, the Anti-Trafficking Act 2003 as amended in 2005

(NAPTIP Act) seeks to protect women and children especially as victims of trafficking and other forms of exploitation.

(2) National Policies on Human Rights

The executive, judiciary and legislature have provided some policies for effective realization of human rights in Nigeria. Some of these include the National Policy on Malaria Control 2005, National Strategic Framework and Plan of Action for VVF Eradication in Nigeria, 2005-2010, National Policy on Food and Nutrition 2001, National Policy on Education 1999 (revised 2004), National Policy on Child and Maternal Health 1994 and Strategic Plan of Action/Implementation Framework 2007/08, National Policy and Guidelines on Gender in Basic Education, 2007. In addition, the provisions of the National Gender Policy 2007, National Reproductive Health Policy and Strategy 2001, National Policy on HIV-AIDS 2003, National Policy on Health 1998 and 2004, the National Policy on the Elimination of FGM 1998 and 2002, National Adolescent Health Policy 1995, National Policy on Maternal and Child Health 1994, constitute the key policy frameworks that seeks to promote the survival, development, protection and participation rights of women and Children to achieve quality reproductive and sexual health in Nigeria.

3.4 National Human Rights Commission in Nigeria

The National Human Rights Commissions was established by the National Human Rights Commission Act, 1995, as amended by the NHRC Act, 2010 in line with Resolution 48/134 of the 1992 United Nations Assembly. It enjoined all member states to establish independent national institutions for the promotion and protection and enforcement of human rights. The Commission serves as an extra-judicial mechanism to safeguard the human rights of the Nigerian citizens. Also, it provides avenues for enlightenment, research and dialogue in order to create awareness on human rights issues.

3.4.1 National Human Rights Commission (Amendment) Act 2010

National Human Rights Act⁸⁴ provide for, among other things, the independence in the conduct of the affairs of the Commission, the funds of the Commission to be a direct charge on the consolidated revenue fund of the federation, establishment of the Human Rights Fund and recognition and enforcement of the awards and recommendation of the Commission as decisions of the High Court. The Commission

⁸⁴ Cap 61 N46 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria, 2004

shall refer any matter of human rights violation requiring prosecution to the Attorney-General of the federation or state for consideration. The Commission is mandated in Section 6 (1), of the Act to:

- (a) Conduct its investigations and inquiries in such a manner as it considers appropriate.
- (b) Institute any civil action on any matter it deems fit in relation to the exercise of its functions under this Act.
- (c) Visit persons, Police Cells and other places of detention to ascertain the conditions thereto and make recommendations to the appropriate authorities.
- (d) Make determinations as to the damages or compensation payable in relation to any violation of human rights where it deems this necessary in the circumstances of the case.
- (e) Co-operate with and consult with other agencies and organizations, governmental and non-governmental organizations.

Also, Section 6 (2) provides that: whenever it appears to the Chairman upon information and after such inquiry as it thinks necessary, that there is reasonable cause to suspect that in any place, there is an evidence of the Court of an offence under this Act, he may by written order direct an officer of the Commission to obtain Court order to:

- (a) Enter upon any law or premises
- (b) Summon and interrogate any person or body or authority to appear before it for the purpose of public inquiry aimed at the resolution of a complain of human rights violations.
- (c) Compel attendance to produce evidences

The law provides in Section 6 (3) that in exercising its functions and powers under this Act, the Commission shall not be subject to any direction or control of any authority or person.

Section 7 (1) also provides: there shall be an Executive Secretary for the Commission which in 7 (c) be appointed by the President subject to confirmation by the Senate. Section 12 (2) states that the fund of the Commission shall be charged on the consolidated revenue fund of the federation.

Section 14 (1) provides that the Court may borrow loan or overdraft from any source, such specific amount as may be required by the Commission for meeting its obligation and discharging its functions under this Act.

Section 15 (1) provides: there is established the Human rights fund which shall be applied by the Commission towards: (a) The conduct of research on human rights issues, and (b) The facilitation of human rights activities of the Commission in collaboration with other human rights, non-governmental organizations, civil society organizations and other stakeholders. The Act provides for the Commission in 18 (2) that no suit shall lie or be instituted in any Court against any member of the Council, Executive Secretary or any Officer or Employee of the Commission for any act done in pursuance or execution of this Act or any other law or enactment or of any public duty or authority or in respect of any alleged neglect or default in the execution of this Act or such law or enactment, duties or authority. Unless the action should commence within 3 months next after the Act, neglect or default complained of or in damage or injury within six months next after the ceasing thereof.

It is stipulated that no suit shall be commenced against any member of the Council, the executive secretary, officer or employee of the Commission before the expiration of one month after written notice to commence the suit shall have been served upon the Commission by the intending plaintiff or his agent”.

Section 22 (1): an award or recommendation made by the Commission shall be recognised as binding and subject to this section and this Act shall upon application in writing to the Court, be enforced by the Court.

The National Human Rights Commission Act (Amendment) 2010 was amended to enhance efficiency in the discharge of the commission’s statutory functions. The salient amendments made are as follows:

- i. That “any existing legislations, administrative provision and proposed bills or bye-laws for the purpose of ascertaining whether such enactments or proposed bills or bye-laws are consistent with human rights norms”⁸⁵. The law requires that the National Assembly in collaboration with the Commission saddle with the responsibility of ensuring all laws relating to human rights are forwarded for the Commission for vetting before consideration by the National Assembly. It is unfortunate that in practice the National Assembly passes laws that are

⁸⁵ Section 5, NHRC Act (Amendment) 2010.

- anchored on human rights without consultation with the Commission. The practice has adversely affected the quality of laws enacted by the legislative arm.
- ii. The Act requires that human rights abuses and violations be it civil or criminal in nature that require prosecution shall be referred to the Attorney General of the Federation or of a State as the case may be.⁸⁶ Since the Commission cannot independently prosecute cases relating to human rights without the consent or approval of the Attorney General of the Federation or State. It is a fundamental impediment in the effective discharge of the Commission's duties. The study recommended that the section should be amended to allow the Commission prosecute all cases without interference by the Attorney General and a caveat should be inserted to checkmate the abuse of the power of prosecution of the Commission after the amendment.
 - iii. The Commission whenever it appears to the Chairman upon information and after such inquiry as they shall think necessary, that there is reasonable cause to suspect that in any place there is evidence of the Commission of any offence under this Act, he may by written order direct an officer of this Commission to obtain a court order to enter any land or premises to obtain evidence or for inspection or taking copies of any document required by the commission. The commission's power to enter premises of any person suspected to have violated human rights by obtaining court leave or permission should be retained.
 - iv. The Act stipulated that in exercising the functions of the commission, it has the power under the Act not to be subjected to the direction or control of any other authority or person⁸⁷. The provision is contradictory to Section 5(5)⁸⁸ which states that approval shall be granted by the Attorney General for the purpose of prosecution of any case relating to human rights in Nigeria, while Section 6(3)⁸⁹ empowers the commission not to be subjected to any authority or adherence to the directive of the executive or the legislature. Therefore, there is a need for the amendment of the sections to provide full fledge autonomy for the commission to enhance its statutory functions.

⁸⁶ Section 5(5), NHRC Act (Amendment) 2010.

⁸⁷ Section 6(3), NHRC Act (Amendment) 2010.

⁸⁸ Section 5 (5), NHRC Act (Amendment) 2010.

⁸⁹ Section 6 (3), NHRC Act (Amendment) 2010.

- v. The amended act provided that it is an offence for any person, body or authority to refuse to comply with lawful directives, determination, decision or finding of the Commission.⁹⁰ In practice, there is challenge of implementation of the commission's recommendation or award. Therefore, there should be stiff penalty for violators of the provision of this Act.
- vi. The amended Act stipulates that award or recommendation made by the Commission shall be recognized as binding and subject to this section and this act shall upon application in writing to the court be enforced by the court. The Court means the Federal High Court or the High Court of the Federal Capital Territory Abuja or the High Court of a State. In practice, there is challenge of implementation of the commission's recommendation or award. Therefore, there should be stiff penalty for violators of the provision of this Act.⁹¹

4.0 LEGAL FRAMEWORK FOR THE PROMOTION AND PROTECTION OF HUMAN RIGHTS IN SOUTH AFRICA

International human rights law has an important role to play in the development of the human rights culture in South Africa. It was applied by a range of institutions and Actors including the Courts, Parliament, the South African Human Rights Commission, Government and Non-governmental organisations.

4.1 The Influence of International Human Rights Law on the Bill of Rights

International human rights law substantially influenced the drafting of the Bill of Rights in the Republic of South African Constitution. The influence of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (1966) and the Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989) is evident in the economic, social and cultural rights and the Children's rights included in the Bill of Rights. Accordingly, in acknowledging and protecting the diversity of language and culture in South Africa, a right was included in the Bill of Rights guaranteeing that persons belonging to cultural, religious or linguistic communities would not be denied the right, with other member of their community, to enjoy their culture, practise their religion and use their language, and to form, join and maintain cultural, religious and linguistic

⁹⁰ Section 6(4), NHRC Act (Amendment) 2010.

⁹¹ Section 22(1), NHRC Act (Amendment) 2010.

associations and other organs of civil society. This clause was modeled on article 27 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (1966).

4.2 South African Human Rights Treaties

South Africa as a country is a party to a number of key international and regional human rights treaties. Since the introduction of democracy, it is currently a party to international human rights treaties such as the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (1966), the International Convention on the Elimination of all forms of Racial Discrimination (1966), the International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (1979), the Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment (1984), the Convention on the Rights of the Child (1984) and the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (1981).⁹² Furthermore, South Africa has signed, but yet to ratify, the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (1966). South Africa is also a party to the Geneva Conventions of 1949 and their two Protocols, the Convention and Protocol Relating to the Status of Refugees, and the Organisation of African Unity Convention Governing Specific Aspects of Refugee Problems in Africa and various conventions adopted under the auspices of the International Labour Organisation.

4.3 Constitution of the Federal Republic of South Africa, 1996

The constitutional history of the Republic of South Africa could be traced to South Africa Act 1909, an Act of the Parliament of the United Kingdom, which unified four British colonies; Cape, Transvaal, Orange River and Natal into the union of South Africa, a self-governing dominion. The Republic of South Africa Constitution Act, 1961 transformed the union into a republic, replacing the Queen with a State President. However, the system of government has not changed as the Act made the then apartheid government completely sovereign. The Republic of South Africa Constitution Act, 1983 approved by only Whites referendum, created the tri-cameral parliament with separate houses representing the white, coloured and Indian people but without representation for black people. The President and Executive Prime Minister were merged into an Executive State President chosen by parliament. The Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1993 or interim Constitution was introduced at the end of apartheid regime to govern the period of transition. The

⁹² African Charter on Human and People's Rights (Ratification & Enforcement) Act Cap A9 LFN 2004.

Constitution made provisions for its liberal democracy, Universal Adult Suffrage, Constitutional Supremacy and Bill of Rights for the first time in the history of South Africa. Another remarkable effort to end the apartheid regime in South Africa was the creation of the new Constitution⁹³. The interim Constitution provided for a parliament made of two houses and contained thirty-four (34) constitutional principles with which the new constitution was required to comply particularly multi-party democracy with regular and universal adult suffrage, supremacy of the Constitution over all other laws, a quasi-federal system in a place of centralized government, non-racism and non-sexism. The protection of all universal fundamental rights, freedoms and civil liberties, equality before the law, separation of powers, impartial judiciary, protection of diversity of languages and cultures. The Bill of Rights now in Chapter Two of the Constitution of South Africa provides for the establishment of a Constitutional Court to interpret the Constitutional provisions particularly Constitutional principles consists of a preamble, fourteen (14) chapters containing 244 sections and eight schedules of the Constitution and other relevant legislations.

The Bill of Rights⁹⁴ enumerates the civil, political, economic, social and cultural human rights of the people of South Africa in which most of the rights apply to anyone in the country with the exception of the right to vote, the right to work and the right to enter the country which only apply to citizens. Everyone is equal before the law and has right to equal protection and the benefit of the law.⁹⁵ The prohibited grounds of discrimination include race, gender, sex, pregnancy, marital status, ethnic or social origin, colour, sex orientation, age, disability, religion, conscience, belief, culture, language and birth. The provision is contradictory since it provides for equality before the law and equal protection. The constitutional exceptions for equality before the law as contained in the South African Constitution is in contradiction of the United Nations Charter on Human Rights which provides for prohibition against discriminations. Consequently, this study recommends that the exceptional clause should be expunged or amended to be in tandem with the international best practices as required by UN Charter for the promotion and protection of human rights. Also, there is right to

⁹³ Act of Parliament No. 108, Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996.

⁹⁴ Chapter II, Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996.

⁹⁵ Section 9, CRSA, 1996.

human dignity;⁹⁶ right to life,⁹⁷ right to freedom and security of the person⁹⁸, freedom from slavery,⁹⁹ servitude or forced labour and fundamental Human rights as enshrined in the Constitution.¹⁰⁰

4.4 The Role of the Judiciary in Interpreting Human Rights in South Africa

The Constitution gives international law a key role in the interpretation of the rights in the Bill of Rights. Thus, a Court, tribunal or forum must consider international law when interpreting the Bill of Rights¹⁰¹. The Constitutional Court has held that international law in this context would include international instruments that are binding on South Africa. The Constitutional Court has referred extensively to international human rights instruments in the course of its judgments: for example, in considering the content and scope of:

1. the right to life in its judgment on the constitutionality of the death penalty;
2. the right against inhuman or degrading punishment in the context of the criminal penalty of juvenile whipping; and
3. the right to establish educational institutions based on a common culture, language or religion.

When interpreting legislation, the courts must also prefer any reasonable interpretation of the legislation that is consistent with international law over any alternative interpretation that is inconsistent with international law.

4.5 Legal Framework of South African Human Rights Commission

The SAHRC is one of the most respected National Human Rights Institutions in Africa. It is well-funded by the State, it enjoys considerable independence, and commands a lot of respect from the population in the country. It is one of the many institutions established in post-apartheid South Africa to address the ills associated by years of racial discrimination in the country.

The Commission was established in 1995, following the coming into force of the Human Rights Act, 1994¹⁰² and the Paris Declaration and to further carry out the

⁹⁶ Section 10, Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996.

⁹⁷ Section 11, CRSA, 1996.

⁹⁸ Section 12, CRSA, 1996.

⁹⁹ Section 13, CRSA, 1996.

¹⁰⁰ Sections 13 to 34, CRSA, 1996.

¹⁰¹ Section 39 (1) (b), CRSA, 1996.

¹⁰² Human Rights Act No. 54 of 1994.

mandates of the United Nations Charter on the Promotion and Protection of Human Rights municipally, regionally and universally. The study considers sections for the appointment of the Commissioners for the Commission¹⁰³ which is the same/similar with the National Human Rights Commission of Nigeria. The appointments of the members of the two Commissions are done by the president subject to the confirmation by the National Assembly. By implication, the President has the absolute discretion to appoint his loyalist at the expense of the National interest of the Country. Nigeria and South Africa had ratified some international human rights Conventions, Covenants and Charters into the municipal laws thereby enhancing the promotion and protection of human rights. These international treaties are as follows: Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1945), Covenant on the Elimination of all Forms of Discrimination against Women (1979), International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, Convention on the Rights of the Child (1989), African Charter on Human and People's Rights, Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment (1984), International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (1966).

4.6 Analysis of the Legal Framework for the Promotion and Protection of Human Rights in South Africa

The thrust of the paper is the analysis of the legal framework for the promotion and protection of human rights in Nigeria and South Africa. Accordingly, the article considered the analysis of the legal framework as follows:

4.6.1 Constitutional Provisions

The evolution of South Africans Humans rights legislation gives ample recognition to past injustices as a defect that the new dispensation seeks to address. All these socio-economic challenges are a consequence of apartheid and colonialism.¹⁰⁴ The Constitutional Court in one of its first decisions after its establishment stated that “race was the basic, all pervading and inescapable criterion for participation by a person in all aspects of political, economic and social life”.¹⁰⁵ In 2017, the SAHRC condemned the income inequality between the blacks and whites, where white households earn

¹⁰³ Section 5(1) – (IV) 2, 3, 4, & 5 (a), South African Human Rights Commission Act, 2013.

¹⁰⁴ Makwati, E. The South African Human rights Commission Legal Resources Centuries, Johannesburg, 744 (CC) Paragraph.

¹⁰⁵ Exparte Chairperson of the Constitutional Assembly: in a re-certification of the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa 1996 4 SA.

four times what black households earn. Also, statistics released by World Bank in 2018 ranked South Africa as the country with the highest economic inequality in the World. In 1993, South Africa enacted a new Constitution, the interim Constitution propelled the Republic into an era of governance based on the principles of rule of law and respect for human rights. By virtue of Section 115 of the interim Constitution that the SAHRC was established and inaugurated on 2 October 1995 under the Human Rights Commission Act. The interim Constitution was repealed in February 1997 when the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa of 1996 came into effect.

The establishment of SAHRC was to serve as a custodian for human rights promotion and protection. The SAHRC were commonly referred to as “Chapter 9” institutions. They were established with the aim of ensuring that South African Constitutional democracy is strengthened. The Court must exercise their powers without fear, favour or prejudice, they should be impartial in the execution of their mandates and be independent and subject only to the country’s Constitution and law.¹⁰⁶ Chapter 9 institutions are accountable to the Republic’s National Assembly and must submit annual reports of their accounts to it.¹⁰⁷ SAHRC is mandated by the Constitution to promote respect for human rights and a culture of human rights, promote the protection, development and attainment of human rights and monitor and assess the observance of human rights in the Republic.¹⁰⁸ The Commission was established on 2nd October, 1995 under the Human Rights Commission Act of 1994 and was subsequently replaced by the South African Human Rights Commission Act 40 of 2014 (SAHRC Act) and as provided for the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa Act 200 of 1993.

The Constitution gives the SAHRC a general and wider power to protect human rights. The institution has powers to investigate and report on the observance of human rights, to take steps to secure appropriate redress where human rights have been violated, to carry out research and to educate people on human rights.¹⁰⁹ These powers are given effect by the SAHRC.¹¹⁰ The SAHRC has broad powers that make it a quasi-judicial institution which allows it to make investigations, subpoena persons,

¹⁰⁶ Section 181 (2) of the CRSA, 1996.

¹⁰⁷ Ibid, Section 181 (5) of the CRSA, 1996.

¹⁰⁸ Ibid, Section 184 (1) (a) – (c) of the CRSA, 1996

¹⁰⁹ See Section 184 (2) of the CRSA, 1996.

¹¹⁰ Act 40 of 2013 (hereafter SAHRC Act).

including members of the executive, institute hearings, and make recommendations. The Commission has power to investigate any activities of the organ of government especially the executive and invite the organ of government and institute any legal action in the event of violations of human rights is a novel provision unlike the Nigerian Law in which the powers of investigation and invitation to appear before it is restrictive and some persons are immune from prosecution especially the new Act which stipulates that, staff of the Commission are not to be charged in Court when carrying out their official assignment even when the official Act was carried out with impunity.

The SAHRC general mandate is the protection of all human rights¹¹¹ and also with special mandate for the protection and realization of socio-economic rights.¹¹² The special mandate is meant to address the socio-economic disadvantages suffered by the majority of South Africans during the apartheid era, when the systematic marginalization of millions of black people resulted in huge economic disparities.¹¹³ SAHRC has additional functions and powers derived from legislative obligations including the Promotion of Equality and the Prevention of Unfair Discrimination Act (PEPUDA or the Equality Act)¹¹⁴ and the Promotion of Access to Information Act (PALA).¹¹⁵ Through these pieces of legislation and its broad powers, the Commission is instrumental in ensuring adherence to the values enshrined in the Bill of Rights.

Human Rights are not the monopoly of one institution, a range of bodies have an interest in advancing human rights promotion and protection. The SAHRC is obliged to liaise with such bodies to ensure that policies and practices are synchronized as far as possible to achieve common objectives or where circumstances warrant cooperation.¹¹⁶ The SAHRC has done well in engendering cooperation with other organization such as the Centre For The Study Of Violence And Reconciliation (CSOR)

¹¹¹ See Section 184 (1) (c) of the Constitution.

¹¹² See D. Horsen, "The Role of played by the South African Human Rights Commission's Economic and Social Rights Reports in Good Governance in South Africa.

¹¹³ Relf, L. C. Building Democratic Institutions: The Role of National Human Rights Institutions Rights Governance.

¹¹⁴ Act 4 of 2000 PEPUDA is the National Legislation mandated by Section 9 (4) of the Constitution and thus enjoys special constitutional status. Significantly, according to its preamble, the Act recognizes the need to address systemic discrimination and specifically aims to achieve the eradication of social and economic inequalities".

¹¹⁵ Act 2 of 2000, the Commission promotes compliance with the PALA and produces an annual report in this regard in line with Section 23-84 of the PAIA.

¹¹⁶ Section 13 (1) b(ii) of the SAHRC Act.

and the LRC in pursuit of shared objectives.¹¹⁷ The SAHRC may review government policies on the promotion of human rights and monitor compliance with international and regional instruments which have a bearing on the Commission's purports and objects.¹¹⁸ The Commission by this means maintains a system of checks on the relevant bodies to ensure that a culture of human rights prevails. The National Human Rights Commission of Nigeria has no special mandate of enforcement of the socio-economic rights which adversely affect the effective discharge of its mandate.

The SAHRC is empowered to make legislative inputs, since the SAHRC Act states that the Commission may recommend to parliament or any other legislature the adoption of any legislation which will give impetus to the promotion of human rights.¹¹⁹ One of the major SAHRC achievements was the ratification of the Optional Protocol to the Covenant Against Torture (OPCAT)¹²⁰ by the South African Parliament¹²¹ which came after years of pressure from the SAHRC and others. Apart from investigation of complaints, the SAHRC also protect people's rights through mediation, conciliation and negotiation with the aim of reaching equitable solutions without resorting to adversarial method of settling disputes. The Chairperson and the Deputy Chairperson of the Commission are appointed by the President on the recommendation of the National Assembly while the Chairperson is the Commission's overall head and executive authority. Section 11 of the SAHRC empowers the Commission to establish standing Committees which are chaired by the Commissioners.¹²²

SAHRC has a binary structure made up of the Commission, whose function is to set out policy, and the Secretariat whose function is policy implementation. The Secretariat is divided into a number of departments namely: legal services, research, human resources, media and communication, finance and administration, education and training. To ensure accessibility of its services, the Commission has offices in each of the country's nine (9) provinces. The composition of the SAHRC is regulated by

¹¹⁷ The SAHRC and the LRC, for example are on the verge of signing a will see them working together towards the implementation of the National Preventive Mechanism, in line with the Optional Protocol to the Convention Against Torture and other Cruel or Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment, 2002 (OPCAT).

¹¹⁸ Ibid, Section 13 (1) (b) (r) of the SAHRC Act.

¹¹⁹ Ibid, Section 13 (2) (a) of the SAHRC Act.

¹²⁰ OPCAT.

¹²¹ Parliament ratified the OPCAT in April 2019 after signing it 13 years prior.

¹²² Section 11 sets out the procedure for the establishment of the Committees.

Section 5 of the SAHRC Act. This provision states that the Commission must have eight Commissioners who must be South African citizens and must be fit and proper persons to hold office in the institution as contemplated in Section 193 (1) of the Constitution and be appointed by the President in terms of Sections 193 (4) and (5) of the Constitution.¹²³ The Commissioners are appointed either on a full-time or part-time basis for a period not exceeding seven (7) years. There may not be less than six (6) permanent Commissioners appointed at any given time and there may not be more than two (2) part-time Commissioners.¹²⁴

The law setting up the SAHRC provides for its appointment mechanisms, powers, mandates, funding as well as accountability measures and independence which means that the law makes it difficult for the SAHRC to be undermined. Section 184 (c) of the Constitution provides that Chapter 9 institutions are independent and subject only to the Constitution and Law.¹²⁵ The legitimacy of the SAHRC derives from the entrenchment in the country first Constitution in the democratic dispensation “legitimacy” encompasses formal guarantees of independence. The Commission has its shortcomings but its legitimacy is unquestionable given its achievements over the years. To uphold the independence of the SAHRC, the law ensures security of tenure and makes provision for members to be appointed through mechanisms that are transparent. The SAHRC provides that Commissioners are appointed on a fixed term determined by the National Assembly although the term does not exceed seven years.¹²⁶

The SAHRC is funded through a vote of the Department of Justice and Constitutional Development (DOJCD) in addition to which the funding is barely adequate, given that 75% of the budget is spent on salaries. The implication of this funding model thus makes the Commission susceptible to financial control, in direct conflict with the Paris Principles. The SAHRC design is a good model for the rest of the continent, but the lack of financial independence adds to several predicaments of the Commission. Besides the failure of the government to recognize that the Commission needs

¹²³ These provisions state among other things that “President on the recommendation of the National Assembly, must appoint the public protection, the Auditor-General and the members of the South African Human Rights Commission”.

¹²⁴ Ibid, Section 5 (2) of the SAHRC Act.

¹²⁵ Ibid, Section 184 (2) of the SAHRC Act.

¹²⁶ Section 5 (2) of the SAHRC Act.

financial autonomy to execute its mandate could be construed as a deliberate attempt to render it ineffective. Truth is that if the Commission has insufficient funding, it would not be able to employ enough competent staff, launch investigations, and institute proceedings in Courts on behalf of victims of human rights violations. This would in turn mean that the SAHRC becomes a White Elephant, one with no shortage of laws and powers, yet without the ability to turn these paper powers into practical use. Powers that can be put to use in the execution of its mandate. A more recent case in which the SAHRC was *amicus curiae* also confirmed the justiciability of socio-economic right. This is the case of residents of *Arhurstone Village v. Amashagana Tribal Authority and Others*.¹²⁷

The NHRC and SAHRC Act were established to be in compliance with the Paris Principles and all the Commissions had substantially complied with the principles. The two Commissions have similar or peculiar impediments affecting the smooth actualization of the mandates of the Commission. Therefore, a robust legal framework of South African Human Rights Commissions which has the constitutional mandate of enforcement and justiciability of socio-economic rights is a lesson for Nigeria to transplant the provision into its municipal laws for enforcement.

5.0 Differences of the National Human Rights Commissions in South Africa and Nigeria

- a) The SAHRC operates in different environment with historical, cultural and ideological differences which adversely affects its operation.
- b) The role of SAHRC is enshrined in the Constitution of South Africa with a special mandate of monitoring and enforcement of socio-economic rights whereas the role of National Human Rights Commission in Nigeria is not enshrined in the Constitution but an Act of National Assembly which can be repealed anytime without cumbersome procedures.

6.0 Similarities of the National Human Rights Commissions in South Africa and Nigeria

The National Human Rights Commissions in South Africa and Nigeria have some similarities based on the legal framework as follows:

- a) established based on the Paris Principles.
- b) Both Commissions have the mandate of promoting and protecting human rights.

¹²⁷(17979/15) (2016) ZAGPPHC 408.

7.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

From the findings, the paper identified the strengths and weaknesses of the legal and institutional framework in Nigeria and South Africa. The study comes to the conclusion that proactive and concrete steps should be taken to tackle the identified challenges. The Government and relevant authorities saddled with the various responsibilities should adhere to the constitutional provisions of promoting and protecting human rights in Nigeria and South Africa. The paper holds that amendments of the existing legal framework would enhance human rights realization in Nigeria and South Africa. Accordingly, government and stakeholders involved in the promotion and protection of human rights should as a matter of urgency put the necessary modalities in place for the amendment of the laws by providing an enabling the environment for the two Commissions to realize their statutory mandates. The paper recommends as follows:

- a. The existing institutional and legal framework in Nigeria and South Africa should be amended for a robust and effective discharge of the statutory mandates of the two Commissions in Nigeria and South Africa.
- b. Nigeria and South African governments should intensify efforts in the provision of social amenities, welfare and security of its citizen in order to enhance the promotion and protection of Human rights in Nigeria and South Africa.
- c. Nigeria and South African governments should establish a specialized Human Rights Court to expeditiously handle human rights cases in Nigeria and South Africa.
- d. There should be a legislative and judicial mechanism in place to support all governmental and non-governmental agencies to effectively collaborate with NHRC and SAHRC in the discharge of their statutory mandates.
- e. The Commissions funding, autonomy, accessibility and enforceability of the awards or recommendations in Nigeria and South Africa should be enhanced by putting in place appropriate executive, legislative and judicial measures to tackle the challenges.